

A Quantum computing approach for multi-objective routing and spectrum assignment optimization [Invited]

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Optimization problems are fundamental in a wide range of fields, including telecommunications, where efficient resource allocation is critical to ensure good network performance and high scalability. In the context of Elastic Optical Networks (EONs), the Multi-Objective Routing and Spectrum Assignment (MO-RSA) problem represents a key challenge, as it involves selecting a valid path and assigning frequency slots while fulfilling continuity and contiguity constraints and optimizing multiple conflicting objectives. This paper presents a novel quantum-based approach to solving the MO-RSA problem. We first formulate the MO-RSA problem as a Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) problem and then solve it using the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA). Our method accounts for both minimizing the total number of used links (or any non-negative additive metric) and maximizing the optical signal-to-noise ratio. For our simulations, we employed the Qiskit framework and IBM's sampler-based quantum backend to implement and test the proposed approach. Our results demonstrate that by encoding the MO-RSA problem into a QUBO model and optimizing it with QAOA, we achieved an approximation ratio of 88% and a computational complexity of $O(n^2)$, which represents a significant improvement over the exponential complexity of traditional integer linear programming methods.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing (QC) is emerging as a new technology capable of solving complex computational problems that have been infeasible to solve using classical approaches. Unlike classical computers, which process information in binary form (0 or 1), quantum computers leverage the principles of quantum mechanics, such as superposition, entanglement, and parallelism, to perform calculations in fundamentally different ways [1]. The ability of quantum computers to process multiple possibilities simultaneously, and to represent complex interactions between variables enables them to approach problem-solving with a computational power that grows exponentially with the number of qubits. These features give QC great potential to address some of the most challenging and computationally demanding tasks in modern science and technology. One of the most promising applications of QC lies in the field of optimization [2–4].

Optimization problems are often NP-Hard because solving them requires examining an exponentially growing number of possibilities as the size of the problem increases. NP-Hard problems belong to the class of problems where verifying a solution

can be done in polynomial time, but finding the optimal solution itself is computationally infeasible as the problem size grows. Most optimization problems involve choosing the best subset from a large set of options which leads to a combinatorial explosion in the number of possibilities [5]. For example, in the traveling salesman problem, finding the shortest route that visits all cities exactly once grows factorially with the number of cities [6]. Moreover, since NP-Hard problems cannot be solved in polynomial time with classical algorithms, finding a solution often requires heuristic methods that may not yield to global optimal solutions. Thus, the NP-Hardness, the combinatorial complexity and the non-deterministic solutions make most of the optimization problems very challenging to solve using conventional methods [7].

In networking, particularly in Elastic Optical Networks (EONs), one of the most challenging optimization problems is Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) [8, 9]. This problem involves finding the optimal path through a network for each request while simultaneously assigning frequency slots (FSs) that do not interfere with other requests [10]. The RSA problem is particularly hard due to the dual complexity of routing and

spectrum assignment, both of which are NP-Hard on their own and become even more challenging when combined [11–13]. Adding to the complexity, RSA is often a multi-objective problem, requiring solutions that not only find feasible paths and assign FSs but also balance goals such as minimizing the number of used links, minimizing spectrum fragmentation, maximizing throughput. In some scenarios, the challenge lies not only in minimizing or maximizing a metric, but also in ensuring that it meets a required threshold based on receiver characteristics and the modulation format. For instance, maintaining Optical Signal-to-Noise Ratio (OSNR) values above a specific threshold is critical to ensure high Quality of Transmission (QoT) [14].

In EONs, each route between a source and a destination can have multiple feasible paths and available FSs. With each additional route and FSs, the number of possible configurations grows exponentially. Moreover, the assignment of FSs for each request must satisfy specific constraints including the spectrum continuity (the same FSs must be available across all links in a chosen path) and the contiguity (the assigned slots must be a contiguous block). Additionally, network demands are often unpredictable, and the RSA solution must adapt dynamically as new requests are added. The non-deterministic nature of the problem and the strong dependency on real-time network conditions make it hard to find an approach that can provide optimal solutions in a reasonable amount of time [9, 10].

QC holds significant promise for optimization problems because of its unique properties, which enable it to navigate complex solution spaces more efficiently than conventional approaches. For example, the superposition property that allows the qubits to exist in multiple states simultaneously gives the quantum computers the ability to represent and process many possible solutions simultaneously, reducing the time needed to find an optimal solution in a large search space. In addition, entanglement enables quantum computers to represent complex interactions between variables, allowing them to model dependencies in optimization problems more naturally and effectively than classical approaches [15, 16].

Usually, the computational power of quantum computers is defined according to their quantum volume, a metric used to express the effectiveness of a given quantum computer including the number of qubits, the quality of the quantum gates, and the error rates. Currently, we are in the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era. The term "noisy" indicates that we do not yet have error correction schemes implemented in the current devices and "intermediate-scale" means that the number of qubits and quantum gates is still relatively modest, limiting the size of the problems that can be solved. One of the most promising developments in the era of NISQ is Variational Quantum Algorithms (VQAs) [17].

VQAs have emerged as leading approaches for achieving quantum advantage on NISQ gate-based computers. The main idea behind these algorithms is to encode the optimization problem into a parameterized quantum circuit, evaluate it on a quantum computer, and then update its parameters using a classical optimizer. This hybrid quantum-classical approach makes VQAs well-suited to handle the constraints of NISQ devices by keeping the quantum circuit depth shallow and mitigating some of the effects of noise. VQAs have been developed for a wide range of applications, including molecular simulation, drug discovery and materials design, finance, and combinatorial optimization [18]. Among the most promising VQAs, we find the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) [19].

QAOA has been specifically designed to run on gate-based

NISQ devices to approximately solve complex combinatorial optimization problems. Since its introduction, QAOA has been applied to a wide range of combinatorial optimization problems, including Max-Cut [20], Boolean satisfiability [21], vehicle routing [22, 23], and the traveling salesman problem [24]. Results from these studies have demonstrated the significant potential of QAOA in addressing these complex problems, offering advantages over classical methods.

In this regard, in this paper, we propose the use of the QAOA to solve the Multi-Objective Routing and Spectrum Assignment (MO-RSA) problem, building on our previous work presented at the ONDM 2024 [25]. In that study, we implemented QAOA to solve the Single-Objective Routing Problem (SORP) and outlined the essential steps for mapping a classical optimization problem onto gate-based quantum computers. However, this current work significantly extends the scope and complexity by tackling the MO-RSA problem, which introduces the optimization of multiple objectives and additional constraints that reflect the real-world demands of EONs. Our contribution can be summarized as follows:

1. We present a general framework in which gate-based NISQ devices can be used to solve MO-RSA in particular by applying QAOA. This is achieved by mapping the problem using Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) formulation.
2. We provide the mathematical formulation of the MO-RSA problem, which includes two objective functions: minimizing the total number of links used and maximizing the OSNR. The formulation also incorporates key constraints, including flow conservation, continuity, contiguity, spectrum capacity, and maximum allowed latency. To validate the proposed formulas, we perform simulations using IBM runtime primitives.
3. By using computational complexity and graph theory, we calculate the time complexity of the proposed solution and define its resource requirements. In particular, we show that the time complexity of our solution scales better compared to an integer linear programming (ILP) model.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we briefly review some of the related work of MO-RSA and its limitations then we explain how this problem can be solved in quantum. Section 3, presents the mathematical formulation and the mapping process used to transfer the MO-RSA from classical to quantum. In section 4, we discuss the simulation results and the time complexity of the proposed scheme compared to an ILP model and future research directions. Section 5 is devoted to conclusions.

2. ROUTING AND SPECTRUM ASSIGNMENT: FROM CLASSICAL TO QUANTUM

Due to the importance of the MO-RSA problem in optical networks, various methods, formulations, and algorithms have been introduced in the literature to address it. In this section, we will briefly review the existing work in this area, discuss its limitations, and explore how QC can be used to solve this problem.

A. Routing and Spectrum Assignment in Classical

In the context of solving the RSA problem and the MO-RSA, several studies have been proposed to find efficient solutions starting from ILP to Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL).

A.1. Related Work

Several studies have used ILP to find optimal or near-optimal solutions for RSA. However, only a few representative works will be mentioned here. In [26], the RSA problem is formulated as an ILP problem that focuses on minimizing the number of used FS in the network. Addressing the need to serve as much traffic as possible within resource limitations, [27] presents ILP models for maximizing the served traffic requests under a given number of FSs. An ILP formulation that minimizes the highest allocated FS index while considering the nonlinear impairments is presented in [28]. Another ILP formulation for RSA that leverages a nonlinear signal distortion model is presented in [29]. The scheme jointly optimizes the selection of modulation formats, carrier frequencies, and power spectral densities to minimize bandwidth usage while guaranteeing the QoT by meeting the signal-to-noise ratio requirements of each channel.

Moreover, there have been several work regarding using enhanced versions of Dijkstra algorithm tailored to the RSA problem. In [30], the authors extended the traditional Dijkstra algorithm by modifying the labeling process, iteration mechanisms, and edge relaxation procedures to fit the specific requirements of optical networks. Building on the top of that study, the authors in [31], proposed a modified version of the generic algorithm proposed in [30], that is able to find the possible ways of finding path pairs in a more efficient way. Moreover, several studies have integrated Dijkstra's algorithm with the first-fit strategy to solve the RSA. The idea behind this approach is to divide the problem into two phases: routing phase where Dijkstra's algorithm is used to route the requests. Then, the spectrum assignment phase that is accomplished by using the first-fit algorithm that takes into consideration the continuity and contiguity constraints. Such approach was presented in [32–34].

ML approaches, especially DRL, have been also applied to address the challenges of RSA. DRL offers a promising approach to handle the complexities of real-time resource allocation by learning optimal decision-making policies through interactions with the network environment. For instance, in [35], the authors proposed a DRL framework where the agent learns the policies to choose the route, the modulation format and to allocate spectrum that minimizes the blocking probability and maximize the resource utilization. To extend the application of DRL to multi-domain EONs, DeepCoop was proposed in [36]. The main idea behind DeepCoop is to assign a dedicated DRL agent to each domain, enabling scalable network automation. These agents make autonomous decisions while sharing limited information to facilitate cooperative decision-making and enhance overall network performance. The work in [37] developed a DRL-based RSA solution that considers end-to-end latency during resource allocation. This approach incorporates latency information into the decision-making process, enabling the DRL agent to select routes and allocate resources in a way that satisfies both bandwidth and latency constraints.

A.2. Limitations

Solving the RSA problem, particularly the MO-RSA, is challenging due to its inherent complexity and dynamic nature. Conventional methods such as ILP models and DRL approaches have significant limitations that prevent their scalability and

adaptability to real-world scenarios. These limitations can be summarized as follows:

- Scalability issue: as the problem scale increases, the number of variables and constraints in the ILP model grows quickly, leading to an exponential increase in the search space. This makes ILP models computationally expensive for large-scale networks. Moreover, while Dijkstra's algorithm is computationally efficient, its performance degrades significantly in large network when combined with repeated spectrum availability and continuity checks.
- Exponential time complexity: Solving ILP models typically requires exponential time, which makes them infeasible for scenarios with numerous requests, edges, or FSs.
- Static nature: ILP models are designed for static scenarios and are not well suited for dynamic or real-time applications, where network conditions and requests change frequently.
- Spectrum Fragmentation: assigning the first available slots without considering their position leads to scattered and fragmented free slots, which reduces the overall network utilization and increases blocking probability for future requests.
- Training and convergence time: training DRL models often requires days to achieve convergence, especially for large-scale RSA problems. This is because the agent must explore a wide range of observation states and receive enough feedback through rewards to learn effective policies.
- Reaction to unseen scenarios: DRL models often struggle to generalize their learned policies to network conditions or traffic patterns not encountered during training, meaning that they may need retraining to accommodate these new traffic patterns, which limit their applicability in dynamic or evolving environments.

Given the aforementioned limitations, there is a clear need for more advanced techniques that can efficiently solve the RSA problem and keep up with the dynamic demands of modern networks, while addressing scalability, adaptability, and multi-objective optimization in a computationally efficient way.

B. Routing and Spectrum Assignment in Quantum

Solving optimization problems with quantum-based approaches is fundamentally different from solving them with classical methods. In this section, we present our approach to solving the MO-RSA problem using the QAOA on gate-based quantum computers.

B.1. Routing and Spectrum Assignment on Gate-Based Quantum Computers

In QC, solving an optimization problem typically involves formulating the cost function as a Hamiltonian, with the optimal solution corresponding to the ground state, or the lowest energy state of this Hamiltonian. When it comes to using VQAs, the goal is to find this ground state by encoding the optimization problem in a way that each possible solution corresponds to a unique energy level. Then, by using a classical optimizer, we iteratively adjust the parameters to bring the system as close as possible to this ground state, effectively minimizing the Hamiltonian. In this context, the Hamiltonian represents the "energy landscape"

Fig. 1. The optimization procedure followed in this paper to map the MO-RSA problem into gate-based quantum computers.

of all potential solutions, where lower energies indicate more optimal configurations. The key stages for this procedure are illustrated in figure 1.

The first step of the procedure is *the input Stage*, where the network topology, decision variables, mathematical formulas (including objective functions and constraints), available FSs, and request requirements are defined.

The second step is *the compilation stage*. This stage is divided into three phases:

- Mapping process: after formulating the problem classically, the next step is to map the problem variables onto qubits, with each qubit representing a binary variable.
- Ansatz construction: in gate-based QC, the Hamiltonian or problem formulation is translated into a series of quantum gates (e.g., X, Y, Z, CNOT) that operate on qubits. This sequence of gates forms what is known as a Variational Quantum Circuit (VQC), which performs operations to evolve the quantum state toward the solution. In our case, this will be achieved through the VQC of the QAOA.
- Ansatz Optimization: the sequence of quantum gates in the circuit should be optimized, with any redundant gates removed to minimize noise and reduce unnecessary computation.

The third step is to run the *hybrid quantum-classical loop*. The VQC is executed on the quantum hardware, where we iteratively update its parameters using a classical optimizer until we find the combination that brings the circuit to the lowest energy state.

Finally, in *the output stage*, the solution to the optimization problem is obtained.

B.2. The Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm

QAOA is a hybrid algorithm proposed by Edward Farhi in 2014 to generate approximate solutions for combinatorial optimization problems [19]. It operates by encoding the cost Hamiltonian of the optimization problem into a quantum circuit. The core structure of a single QAOA layer contains two Hamiltonians (also known as Hermitian operators) as illustrated in figure 2: *the Cost Hamiltonian*, which encodes the cost function of the optimization problem, and *the Mixer Hamiltonian*, which facilitates transitions between states to expand the solution space.

Fig. 2. The fundamental building blocks of the QAOA circuit with p layers.

Usually, the performance of QAOA is measured by the approximation ratio $\left| \frac{\text{QAOA value}}{\text{Optimal value}} \right|$, which represents the ratio of the cost associated with the solution found by QAOA to the true optimal solution. Theoretically, this approximation ratio increases as the number of layers p increases, and it also depends on the quality of the parameters suggested by the classical optimizer during the optimization loop [19, 38].

3. QAOA APPLIED TO MO-RSA

In EONs, considering a multi-objective approach for RSA is essential to effectively address the complexity of network demands. In our work, we focus on two key objectives: minimizing the total number of links used and maximizing the OSNR. These two objectives are chosen to balance efficient resource use while accounting for physical layer impairments, ensuring a high QoT. In this regard, in this section, we describe the network model adopted and the mathematical formulation alongside the mapping process used.

A. Network Modeling

An EON is modeled as a directed graph $G = (V, E, m)$, where V represents the set of nodes (i.e., optical switches, or ROADMs), E the set of optical links (i.e., single-mode optical fibers), $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ the number of FSs on each edge. We define $d_{i,j}$ as the delay between nodes i and j and $s_{i,j}^m$ as the set of FSs that can be allocated in each fiber link within E as shown in figure 3. The width of each FS is set to 12.5 GHz. Additionally,

we define R as the set of traffic requests. Each request $r_i \in R$ is characterized by a tuple $(s_i, d_i, v(r_i), l_{r_i})$, where s_i is the source, d_i is the destination, $v(r_i)$ is the volume of the request (e.g., the requested number of slots needed) and l_{r_i} is the maximum allowed latency.

In this paper, we consider contentionless, directionless, and colorless (CDC) ROADMs in transparent optical networks. For the OSNR estimation, we used the values and the formulas presented in [14]. The formula to calculate the total OSNR is:

$$\text{Total OSNR} = \frac{1}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{\text{Link_OSNR}_j}\right) + \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{1}{\text{Node_OSNR}_j}\right)} \quad (1)$$

Where the *Link_OSNR* accounts for the total Amplifier Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noise generated by all the amplifiers spans on a link $\{i, j\}$. Meanwhile, the *Node_OSNR* considers the ASE noise introduced by the booster amplifier at each node.

Following the steps presented in the paper [14], the *Node_OSNR* = 31.9 dB, while the *Link_OSNR* will vary depending on the length of the optical fiber as shown in table 1.

Table 1. The characteristic associated with each edge of the graph

Edges	Characteristics
0 → 1	Length = 240 km ; Link_OSNR = 25.14 dB
0 → 2	Length = 160 km ; Link_OSNR = 26.89 dB
0 → 3	Length = 320 km ; Link_OSNR = 23.9 dB
1 → 3	Length = 80 km ; Link_OSNR = 29.87 dB
2 → 3	Length = 240 km ; Link_OSNR = 25.14 dB

Therefore, the OSNR from node i to node j will be calculated as $\frac{1}{\text{OSNR}_{i \rightarrow j}} = \frac{1}{\text{OSNR}_i} + \frac{1}{\text{OSNR}_{i,j}}$. These values are illustrated in figure 3.

Fig. 3. EON graph used in this paper where the blue slots represent the available FSs that can be allocated while the red FSs represent the FSs that are already occupied by the previous requests.

It is important to mention that the OSNR estimation presented here follows a straightforward approach, serving as a proof-of-concept for our proposed methodology. More advanced OSNR calculation techniques are available in the state-of-the-art literature, offering higher precision by considering various

physical layer impairments and nonlinear effects [39, 40]. However, for the purposes of this study, we chose these simplified formulas to focus on validating our model and its practical applicability. This choice allows us to demonstrate our approach effectively without the added complexity of comprehensive OSNR modeling.

B. Problem Formulation

Usually, the mathematical formulation process of an optimization problem consists of finding three main components: decision variables, objective functions, and constraints. In the case of the RSA problem, the decision variable we will be using in this paper is:

$$x_{i,j}^m = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if request } r_i \text{ uses the slot } m \text{ on edge } (i, j) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Because we are dealing with a multi-objective optimization problem, the objectives we want to optimize are:

- Objective 1:** minimize the total number of links used for routing requests in the network. This is achieved by minimizing the following objective function:

$$\text{minimize} \quad \sum_{r_i \in R} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{s=1}^m \frac{s_{i,j}^m}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m \quad (3)$$

- Objective 2:** minimize the total OSNR. Although a higher OSNR is generally preferred, we formulate the objective as a minimization problem to fit the structure of our optimization model. This is achieved by minimizing the following expressions:

$$\text{minimize} \quad \sum_{r_i \in R} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{s=1}^m \frac{s_{i,j}^m}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m \frac{1}{\text{OSNR}_{i,j}} \quad (4)$$

where $v(r_i)$ represents the volume of the request r_i , $x_{i,j}^m$ is a binary variable, and $s_{i,j}^m$ is the spectrum slot usage on link (i, j) for FS index m .

The RSA problem is divided into two sub-problems. The routing part is where we need to find a fully connected path. The spectrum assignment part where we need to assign a number of requests FSs (known as the super channel) that has to be continuous (i.e., the indices of the assigned FSs should be the same on the whole lightpath), contiguous (i.e., the assigned FSs have to be adjacent). Moreover, for each request $r_i = (s_i, d_i, v(r_i), l_{r_i})$, we have a number of FSs slots that need to be allocated and a maximum allowed latency that the transmission time cannot exceed. The mathematical formulations of these constraints are:

- Flow conservation:** it includes the main three routing constraints that are the source constraint (i.e., the source node has to have more outgoing than incoming edges), the destination constraint (i.e., the destination node has more incoming than outgoing edges) and the path connectivity constraint to ensure that the chosen path is fully connected. This is achieved by the formulas:

$$\begin{cases} H_s = \sum_j x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - 1, \text{ if } i = \text{src} \\ H_d = \sum_k x_{k,i}^m s_{k,i}^m - 1, \text{ if } i = \text{dst} \\ H_p = \sum_{i \neq s,d} \left(\sum_j x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - \sum_k x_{k,i}^m s_{k,i}^m \right) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

- **Slot capacity:** This constraint ensure that a FS can be assigned to only one request (avoiding interference with other requests).

$$s_{i,j}^m = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if a slot } m \text{ is available} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

- **Contiguity constraint:** for all $r_i \in R$, the slots assigned should be next to each other. It is formulated as:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} (x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - x_{i,j}^{m+1} s_{i,j}^{m+1}) \quad (7)$$

- **Continuity constraint:** for all $r_i \in R$, the indices of the assigned slots should stay the same. This constraint is satisfied by fulfilling the constraints in equations (6) and (7).
- **The exact fit constraint:** for all $r_i \in R$, we need to allocate exactly the number of requested FSs (i.e., the request volume). This is formulated as:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - v(r_i) \right) \quad (8)$$

- **Maximum allowed latency:** this constraint ensures that the total latency of the selected path does not exceed a certain threshold l_{r_i} . It is formulated as:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} \frac{d_{i,j}}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m \leq l_{r_i} \quad (9)$$

C. Mapping Process

Following the optimization pipeline illustrated in the previous section, the next step will be to map these formulas into quantum hardware. One of the most used techniques is the Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) program (a.k.a unconstrained binary quadratic programming (UBQP)) [41].

QUBO is a mathematical model that has been widely used to map combinatorial optimization problems onto quantum devices including quantum annealers and gate-based models[42]. One of the biggest advantages of using QUBO is that it translates complex optimization objectives and constraints into one compact quadratic cost function, where the goal is to minimize it or maximize it. Moreover, QUBO models use binary variables, which align well with the qubit representation in QC. Each binary variable in a QUBO corresponds to a qubit, allowing direct and natural mapping. This binary nature simplifies the process of encoding the problem onto quantum hardware.

The mathematical formula of QUBO is represented as:

$$\min_X XQX^T + C^T X \quad (10)$$

Here, Q is an $N \times N$ matrix representing the quadratic part, C is a vector of length N representing the linear part, and X is the binary variable. To solve a QUBO, we need to find the combination of X that minimizes equation (10).

For our RSA problem, we will follow this approach to develop a compact cost function that combines both the objective functions and constraints. By converting each constraint into a penalty term and applying a quadratic transformation, we can represent the entire problem within a single QUBO model.

The total Hamiltonian cost function of the RSA problem formulated as a QUBO model is represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle H_c \rangle = \min & \left[P_s \left(\sum_{i \in N} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - 1 \right)^2 + P_d \left(\sum_{j \in N} x_{j,D}^m s_{j,D}^m - 1 \right)^2 \right. \\ & + P_{\text{path}} \sum_{i \notin \{S,D\}} \left(\sum_j x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - \sum_k x_{k,i}^m s_{k,i}^m \right)^2 \\ & + P_{\text{contiguity}} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} (x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - x_{i,j}^{m+1} s_{i,j}^{m+1})^2 \\ & + P_{r_i} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - v(r_i) \right)^2 \\ & + P_{\text{latency}} \left(\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} \frac{d_{i,j}}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m - l_{r_i} \right)^2 \\ & + \alpha_1 \sum_{r_i \in R} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{s=1}^m \frac{s_{i,j}^m}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m \\ & \left. + \alpha_2 \sum_{r_i \in R} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{s=1}^m \frac{s_{i,j}^m}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m \frac{1}{\text{OSNR}_{i,j}} \right] \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

In this formulation, each P represents penalty terms associated with their respective constraints. the parameters α_1 and α_2 represent the decision maker's preference, with higher values indicating higher priority and $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 1$.

The *maximum allowed latency* constraint (9) is an inequality constraint. Typically, converting this type of constraint into a penalty would require the introduction of additional variables, known as *slack variables*. However, for simplicity and practical reasons, we chose to integrate it directly as a penalty.

To extract the components of the QUBO model, we simply need to reorder and group the quadratic terms (to form Q) and the linear terms (to form C), while representing the X vector with the RSA decision variables $x_{i,j}^m$. These components can be represented as:

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} (Q_{0,1}^1)^2 & Q_{0,1}^1 \times Q_{0,1}^2 & \dots & Q_{0,1}^1 \times Q_{2,3}^1 & Q_{0,1}^1 \times Q_{2,3}^2 \\ 0 & (Q_{0,1}^2)^2 & \dots & Q_{0,1}^2 \times Q_{2,3}^1 & Q_{0,1}^2 \times Q_{2,3}^2 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & Q_{0,2}^1 \times Q_{2,3}^1 & Q_{0,2}^1 \times Q_{2,3}^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & (Q_{2,3}^1)^2 & Q_{2,3}^1 \times Q_{2,3}^2 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & (Q_{2,3}^2)^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$X^T = \begin{bmatrix} X_{0,1}^1 \\ X_{0,1}^2 \\ X_{0,1}^3 \\ X_{0,1}^4 \\ \vdots \\ X_{j,D}^{M-1} \\ X_{j,D}^M \end{bmatrix}, \quad C^T = \begin{bmatrix} c_{0,1}^1 \\ c_{0,1}^2 \\ c_{0,1}^3 \\ c_{0,1}^4 \\ \vdots \\ c_{j,D}^{M-1} \\ c_{j,D}^M \end{bmatrix}$$

In our case, the Q matrix is an upper triangular matrix of size $K \times K$, where the main diagonal elements represent the values derived from the quadratic terms $(x_{i,j}^m)^2$. The non-zero off-diagonal elements correspond to the interactions between qubits, representing the FSs in our case. The matrix is upper triangular because the interactions between the variables are symmetric, so we replaced all the $Q_{i,j}^m$ by $Q_{i,j}^m + Q_{j,i}^m$ in order to avoid redundant representation of symmetric interactions and optimizing more the computational time.

The coefficients in the vector C^T correspond to the linear terms derived from $x_{i,j}^m$. Both C^T and X have a length of K , where K represents the total number of available FSs in the network, which, in our case, is 11.

D. The equivalent QAOA Ansatz of the MO-RSA

Following the steps in the optimization pipeline, after the mapping process, we need to construct the QAOA Ansatz of the MO-RSA.

Fig. 4. The equivalent QAOA Ansatz for the MO-RSA problem, with the cost Hamiltonian shown in orange and the mixer Hamiltonian in green.

For space efficiency, the circuit in figure 4 corresponds to the first four FSs in our graph (i.e., $x_{0,1}^1, x_{0,1}^2, x_{0,1}^3, x_{0,1}^4$) where each FS is represented by a qubit.

The first layer of the circuit initializes the qubits in the state $|H_i\rangle$ using Hadamard gates (H) to place them in an equal superposition.

The second layer corresponds to the *Cost Hamiltonian* (in orange), this layer consists of two types of gate:

- The R_z gate is a single-qubit gate that applies a rotation around the z -axis by an angle of $c_i\gamma$, where c_i represents the components of the C vector in the QUBO formulation.
- The R_{zz} gate is a two-qubits gate that applies a phase shift around the z -axis by angle of $\gamma Q_{i,j}$ and representing interactions between qubits (or FSs in our case), where $Q_{i,j}$

represents the components of the Q matrix in the QUBO formulation.

The last layer of the circuit is the *Mixer Hamiltonian* (shown in green). It consists of single-qubit R_x gates that perform rotations around the x -axis by an angle of 2β . This layer enables the quantum algorithm to explore different configurations (states) of the problem by navigating through its search space.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

After formulating the problem, mapping it using QUBO, and constructing the equivalent QAOA ansatz, the next step is to execute the circuit on the quantum hardware and extract the results.

A. Case Study and Simulation Results

Fig. 5. The assigned FSs and the path selected by the QAOA are highlighted in green.

To validate the proposed methodology, we conducted simulations using *Qiskit* which is an open-source software development kit (SDK) that provides tools for creating and running quantum programs on prototype quantum devices. Due to the current limited access to quantum hardware, we will use the *IBM Qiskit Runtime Sampler primitive* to run the circuit. The Sampler primitive is a high-level abstraction provided by the IBM Qiskit Runtime service, allowing users to submit quantum circuits for execution. It then computes the probability (or quasi-probability) distribution of measuring each possible bitstring as an outcome [43]. To update the parameters of the circuit, we will be using COBYLA as our classical optimizer.

For results visualization, we present the outcomes based on the graph shown in figure 3. The penalty coefficients were set as follows: $P_s = P_d = P_{path} = 50$, $P_{contiguity} = 80$ and $P_{r_i} = P_{latency} = 100$. We chose $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0.5$ for the objective functions to obtain an intermediate path that balances both objectives. The request is defined as $r_i = (0, 3, 2 \text{ FSs}, 5 \text{ ms})$, meaning we need to send data from node 0 to node 3, assign two FSs, and ensure the total transmission time is less than 5 ms. For this case of study, we choose to work with a circuit of depth $p = 1$.

Figure 5 illustrates the lighthouse path identified by the QAOA. The slots highlighted in green (i.e., $x_{0,1}^1, x_{0,1}^2, x_{1,3}^1, x_{1,3}^2$) are those selected by the algorithm to assign to the request r_i . These slots successfully meet all the constraints mentioned previously while balancing the two objective functions, resulting in a total transmission time of 4 ms and a total OSNR of 29.42 dB.

In optimization problems involving n elements, the solution space is represented by a 2^n -dimensional Hilbert space, where each dimension corresponds to a computational basis state $|X\rangle$.

Fig. 6. The probability distribution of the possible path solutions and their corresponding energy values.

In our case, these elements represent the spectrum slots, meaning we have $2^{11} = 2048$ basis states (i.e., combinations). To analyze and visualize the probability distribution, we focus on the top 10 basis states sampled from the final quantum states

Figure 6 shows the distribution of these quantum states over the different computational basis states. Each bitstring on the y-axis represents a possible combination of spectrum slots allocated to the selected lightpaths. The length of each bar in the diagram reflects the probability of obtaining the corresponding bitstring when sampling from the quantum state. The cost function values (i.e., energy values) corresponding to these bitstrings are shown on the right-hand side. The bar colors indicate the energy levels observed during the simulation, with yellow representing higher energy values and purple denoting the lowest energy values. The bitstring $|11000011000\rangle$ displayed a higher sampling probability of 4.4 % compared to the others with a minimum energy of -2859.5. This bitstring corresponds to the optimal solution which involves allocating FSs $x_{0,1}^1, x_{0,1}^2, x_{1,3}^1, x_{1,3}^2$ along the path $0 \rightarrow 1$ and $1 \rightarrow 3$ as was shown in Figure 5. It is important to keep in mind that, although 4.4% may seem low, it is quite significant given the $2^{11} = 2048$ possible combinations in the solution space.

As mentioned in Section B.2, one way to measure the performance of QAOA is by calculating the approximation ratio:

$$\text{Approximation ratio} = \left| \frac{\text{QAOA value}}{\text{Optimal value}} \right| = \left| \frac{-2859.5}{-3260} \right| = 0.877$$

The optimal value was calculated using a brute force approach, ensuring the exact solution. The resulting approximation ratio of approximately 88% demonstrates the effectiveness of QAOA, especially considering that we used $p = 1$, which corresponds to a shallow circuit depth. This indicates that even

with minimal circuit depth, QAOA provides a high-quality approximation.

B. Time Complexity Analysis

In computational complexity theory, algorithms are evaluated based on their asymptotic behavior, particularly how their performance scales as the input size increases. One of the most reasonable ways to compare a quantum approach against a classical approach is by analyzing their time complexity and scalability. To better understand the performance of a classical method, we will formulate a basic RSA problem as an ILP model and analyze its behavior. Then, we will compare both approaches, considering the number of decision variables, the number of constraints, and their time complexity.

The ILP model is defined as follows [44]:

$$\min \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{e \in E} y_{re} \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{e \in \delta^-(s(r))} y_{re} - \sum_{e \in \delta^+(s(r))} y_{re} = 1 \quad \forall r \in R \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{e \in \delta^-(j)} y_{re} - \sum_{e \in \delta^+(j)} y_{re} = 0 \quad \forall r \in R, \forall j \in V \setminus \{s(r), t(r)\} \quad (14)$$

$$y_{re} + x_{rs} + y_{r'e} + x_{r's} \leq 3 \quad \forall r, r' \in R, r \neq r' \quad (15)$$

$$a_{rs} \geq a_{r,s+1} \quad \forall r \in R, \forall s \in S \setminus \{S\} \quad (16)$$

$$b_{rs} \geq b_{r,s-1} \quad \forall r \in R, \forall s \in S \setminus \{1\} \quad (17)$$

$$x_{rs} + a_{rs} + b_{rs} = 1 \quad \forall r \in R, \forall s \in S \quad (18)$$

$$B \sum_{s \in S} x_{rs} \geq v(r) \quad \forall r \in R \quad (19)$$

In this formulation, the variable y_{re} is binary and represents whether edge e is assigned to request r ($y_{re} = 1$) or not ($y_{re} = 0$). The variable x_{rs} is also binary and indicates whether request r uses slot s ($x_{rs} = 1$). To ensure slot contiguity, a_{rs} and b_{rs} are binary variables representing whether request r uses slots greater than s ($a_{rs} = 1$) or slots smaller than s ($b_{rs} = 1$), respectively. Finally, $v(r)$ is a positive integer that denotes the volume of request r , which corresponds to the number of slots required to fulfill the request.

The objective function (12) aims to minimize the number of used links. Constraints (13) and (14) express the classic law of conservation of flows. Constraint (15) ensures that no slot is shared by two demands that use the same link. Constraints (16) and (17) ensure that channels are formed by consecutive slots. Constraint (18) ensures that a frequency slot is uniquely assigned, while constraint (19) guarantees demand satisfaction.

Usually, the time complexity of an ILP model depends on the number of variables, denoted as n , and the number of constraints denoted as m [45]. For the provided ILP formulation:

- Number of variables: the total number of variables is $n \approx |R| \times |E| (1 + 3 \times |S|)$ Where R is the number of requests and S is the number of FSs in the network which includes:
 - y_{re} : Binary variable for edge assignment $|R| \times |E|$
 - x_{rs} : Binary variable for slot usage $|R| \times |E| \times |S|$
 - a_{rs} and b_{rs} : Binary variables for contiguity $2 \times |E| \times |S|$
- Number of constraints: the total number of constraints $m \approx |R| \times (|V| - 1) + |R|^2 \times |E| \times |S| + 2 \times |R| \times |S| + |R|$ with:
 - Flow conservation constraints $|R| \times (|V| - 1)$
 - Slot sharing constraints $|R|^2 \times |E| \times |S|$
 - Slot contiguity constraints $2 \times |R| \times |S|$
 - Request satisfaction constraint $|R|$
- Search space: the search space of the ILP models is exponential in the number of variables, in our case it is search space = 2^n
- Time complexity: the theoretical time complexity of solving the ILP model is $O(2^n \times \text{poly}(m))$. In our case, the complexity is dominated by the term $O(2^n)$

For a more in-depth discussion about the computational complexity of ILP models, we refer the reader to the work in [46–49].

In the case of our QAOA-QUBO approach, the time complexity is estimated as follows:

- Number of variables: in our formulation the main decision variable is x_{ij}^m which indicates whether a request r_i uses slot m on edge (i, j) . x_{ij}^m depends on the number of requests R , edges E and spectrum slots S , thus the total number of variables is $n = |R| \times |E| \times |S|$.
- Number of constraints: the total number of constraints is $m = |E| \times |S| + |R| \times (|V| - 1) + (|R| \times |E| \times (S - 1)) + |R| \times |S| + |R| \times |S|$ which includes:
 - Spectrum capacity: $|E| \times |S|$

- Flow conservation: $|R| \times (|V| - 1)$
- Contiguity constraint: $(|R| \times |E| \times (S - 1))$
- Exact fit constraint: $|R| \times |S|$
- Maximum allowed latency: $|R| \times |S|$

- Search space: Since our decision variable x_{ij}^m is binary, the search space is $2^n = 2^{|R| \times |E| \times |S|}$
- Time complexity: to calculate the time complexity of our approach, we need to go through the full optimization process, that is:
 - Constructing the QUBO: the dominant part in formulating the QUBO is the population of the Q matrix. Since the size of the Q matrix is $n \times n$ (i.e., $|S| \times |S|$), the overall complexity is $O(n^2)$.
 - Running the QAOA Ansatz: the complexity of the QAOA circuit depends on the depth of the circuit p and the number and the commutation property of the quantum gates. This property is critical in quantum circuit optimization as it allows for the parallel execution of gates [50]. The dominant complexity of the circuit is $O(\log(n))$, calculated as follows:
 - * H gates: applying the H gates to all the qubits resulting on time complexity of $O(n)$.
 - * R_z gates: since the R_z gates commute, they can be executed in parallel resulting in time complexity of $O(1)$.
 - * R_{zz} gates: since R_{zz} gates commutes when acting on different pairs of qubits, we can also execute them in parallel. Their time complexity in the case of maximum parallelism is $O(\log(n))$.
 - * R_x gates: the mixer Hamiltonian gates can also be executed in parallel resulting in a time complexity of $O(1)$.
 - Classical optimizer: optimizing the QAOA parameters scales linearly with the number of the circuit's layers, which gives a complexity of $O(2p)$.

Thus the dominant time complexity of the QUBO-QAOA approach is $O(n^2)$.

Table 2, summarizes this comparison for $R = 1$.

Table 2. * Comparison between the ILP model and the QUBO-QAOA model

Metrics	ILP model	QUBO-QAOA model
Variables	$(E + 3 \times S)$	$ E \times S $
Constraints	$ S \times (E + 2)$	$ E \times (2 \times S - 1)$
Search space	$2^{(E +3 \times S)}$	$2^{ E \times S }$
Time complexity	$O(2^{ E +3 \times S })$	$O(S^2)$

* In this table, we considered the dominant terms.

C. Discussion

When comparing the ILP model to the QUBO-QAOA approach, the difference in the time complexity is a critical factor. The ILP model has an exponential time complexity, quickly becoming infeasible as the problem size increases. For instance, with just 10 edges and 10 slots per edge, the ILP model would need approximately 1.27×10^{30} operations, a number that is so large that even the most advanced classical solvers, such as Gurobi or CPLEX, would struggle significantly to converge to an optimal solution. On the other hand, the QUBO-QAOA approach, with its quadratic time complexity, would require only 100 operations for the same problem size, making it more practical.

An important advantage of the QUBO formulation is its ability to integrate all constraints and multiple objective functions into a single, compact mathematical representation. This integration not only reduces the overall complexity but also ensures that the computational cost remains independent of the number of objective functions. This is particularly beneficial in scenarios where multiple trade-offs, such as latency and OSNR, need to be considered simultaneously.

However, it is important to note that comparing quantum approaches like the QUBO-QAOA to classical methods is not straightforward. QC is still in its early stage, with fault-tolerance or mature enough quantum hardware not yet available. As a result, the full potential of quantum methods especially in the networking and optimization fields, cannot yet be realized or directly compared to classical approaches. Nevertheless, the promising scalability of the QUBO-QAOA approach highlights its potential as a viable solution for large-scale optimization problems.

D. Future Research Directions

One of the aspect we aim to refine is how we handled the maximum allowed latency constraint in our current formulation. In this study, we addressed this by introducing a large penalty to the QUBO constraint whenever the latency exceeds its limit. Even though this method is effective, it can sometimes lead to overly rigid constraints. A more efficient approach will be to introduce slack variables, which can offer more flexibility by allowing small violations of the latency at a controlled cost. This would make the formulation more adaptable to varying network conditions and improve its overall practicality. Usually, for a "a less than or equal \leq " type of constraint, we need to introduce a non-negative slack variable to represent the gap between the function and the threshold [51]. The maximum allowed latency constraint, in this case, can be formulated as:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} \frac{d_{i,j}}{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m + z_{r_i} = l_{r_i} \quad (20)$$

With z_{r_i} is a non-negative integer slack variable that measure how much room left between the two sides of the constraint. Since slack variables are integers, representing them in a QUBO formulation and mapping them to quantum circuits will require multiple qubits depending on the range of the slack variable.

Another important direction for future work is the formulation of the OSNR constraint. Typically, OSNR is represented as an inequality constraint, where each request is associated with a threshold OSNR that must not be exceeded to ensure acceptable QoT. This can be expressed as:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{m=1}^{v(r_i)} x_{i,j}^m s_{i,j}^m \frac{1}{Total_OSNR} \leq \frac{1}{Threshold_OSNR} \quad (21)$$

In our current formulation, OSNR is simplified and treated as an objective function. However, representing it as a formal inequality constraint would bring the model closer to real-world scenarios. This adjustment would allow us to better account for physical layer impairments and ensure compliance with practical optical network standards.

We adopted these simplifications due to the current limitations in accessing proper quantum hardware and the challenges associated with implementing complex constraints in the available quantum computing frameworks. Additionally, our main goal is to make the first step toward integrating QC-based approaches into network optimization.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a quantum optimization approach tailored for near-term gate-based quantum computers to efficiently address the MO-RSA problem in EONs. We developed a mathematical formulation of the problem and converted it into a QUBO model, enabling its implementation on gate-based quantum computers using the QAOA. Our approach effectively balances the conflicting objectives of minimizing the total number of links and maximizing the OSNR, ensuring efficient resource utilization and high QoT. By using the Qiskit framework and IBM's sampler-based quantum backend, we achieved an approximation ratio of 88% and a quadratic computational complexity of $O(S^2)$, where S is the number of frequency slots in the network. This represents a significant improvement over the exponential complexity of traditional ILP models. This work serves as a foundational step toward integrating QC techniques into network optimization problems, particularly in the context of EONs. As the complexity of optimization problems in EONs continues to grow, driven by the demands of emerging 6G applications and their stringent requirements, QC offers a promising option to tackle these challenges efficiently.

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